

Comparative Evaluation of Fracture Strength Recovery of Reattached Anterior Fractured Tooth Fragment Using Different Reattachment Techniques and Adhesives: An In Vitro Study

Zalak Jain¹
Sonal Bansal²
V.K. Shetty³
Saleha Parveen⁴
Milan Sikarwar⁵

PG Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor²
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor & Head³
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁵
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

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Abstract

Background: Traumatic fractures of anterior teeth are common and can adversely affect aesthetics, function, and psychological well being. Fragment reattachment is a conservative treatment modality, and its success largely depends on the reattachment technique and bonding system used.

Aim: To evaluate and compare the fracture strength of reattached anterior tooth fragments using external chamfer and internal dentinal groove techniques with 5th and 7th generation bonding agents.

Materials and Methods: Eighty extracted maxillary anterior teeth were selected and divided into three groups: external chamfer (n=32), internal dentinal groove (n=32), and control (n=16). Experimental groups were further subdivided based on the bonding agent used. Standardized incisal fractures were created, and fragments were reattached using the respective techniques. Fracture resistance was tested using a universal testing machine. Data were analyzed using SPSS with one way ANOVA, post hoc Tukey test, and Student's t-test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results: The control group showed the highest fracture strength. No significant difference was observed between the two main reattachment techniques. However, subgroup analysis revealed significant differences, with the internal dentinal groove combined with a 7th generation bonding agent demonstrating the highest fracture resistance among experimental groups, while the internal groove with 5th generation bonding agent showed the lowest values.

Conclusion: Fragment reattachment is a reliable and conservative treatment option, though it does not fully restore the strength of intact teeth. Both reattachment technique and bonding agent significantly influence fracture resistance. The internal dentinal groove technique with a 7th generation bonding agent showed superior performance, highlighting the importance of appropriate technique and material selection.

Keywords: Fragment reattachment, fracture strength, external chamfer, internal dentinal groove, bonding agents, anterior teeth.

Introduction

Traumatic fractures of anterior teeth are common, especially in children and young adults, and can significantly affect function, aesthetics, and psychological well being. Modern management focuses on preserving natural tooth structure and restoring appearance through conservative methods such as fragment reattachment when the fractured piece is available.¹

This technique offers excellent aesthetics, minimal preparation, reduced treatment time, and emotional benefits to patients. Various

reattachment methods, including external chamfer and internal dentinal groove, have been introduced to improve strength and durability, but no clear consensus exists regarding the best approach.

Advances in adhesive dentistry have also led to the development of different generations of bonding agents. Fifth generation bonding agents provide high bond strength but are technique sensitive, whereas seventh

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generation agents simplify clinical steps but may have lower long-term durability.²

Therefore, this study was undertaken to compare the fracture strength of reattached anterior teeth using external chamfer and internal dentinal groove techniques with 5th and 7th generation bonding agents to determine the most effective method for clinical success.

Methodology

A total of 80 freshly extracted maxillary anterior teeth were selected for this in vitro study. The teeth were cleaned and stored in 0.9% saline solution to prevent dehydration.

Only permanent maxillary anterior teeth with intact crown and root morphology and fully developed apices were included. Teeth exhibiting caries, fractures, cracks, previous restorations, developmental anomalies, or intrinsic discoloration were excluded from the study.

The samples were divided into three groups:

Group 1 external chamfer technique (n=32),

Group 2 internal dentinal groove technique (n=32),

Group 3 control group (n=16).

Groups 1 and 2 were further subdivided based on bonding agents into 5th generation and 7th generation subgroups.

The study consisted of THREE procedures:

1. Sectioning of incisal third of sound teeth

The labial surface of each tooth was divided into three equal parts, and the incisal third was sectioned (except in control teeth) using a diamond disc under cooling to simulate an Ellis Class II fracture. The fragments were cleaned with sodium hypochlorite and water, and both fragments and teeth were stored in 0.9% saline to prevent dehydration before bonding.

2. Reattachment of the fragment using different techniques

Fractured fragments were reattached using two techniques external chamfer and internal dentinal groove with 5th and 7th generation bonding agents.

Group I - External Chamfer

In Group 1, fragments were first bonded using nano-hybrid composite, followed by preparation of a 1 mm circumferential chamfer at the fracture line, which was restored with flowable composite and then finished and polished.

Fig 1. Chamfer line preparation

Fig 2. Specimen after finishing and polishing

In Subgroup 1A, reattachment was performed using a 5th generation bonding agent. The tooth and fragment surfaces were etched with 37% phosphoric acid for 15 seconds, rinsed, and gently air dried. The adhesive was then applied and light cured. A nano-hybrid composite was placed on the fractured surfaces, and the fragment was repositioned followed by staged light curing.

In Subgroup 1B, reattachment was performed using a 7th generation bonding agent applied to the tooth structure for 10 seconds and light cured for 20 seconds. A nano-hybrid composite was placed on the fractured surfaces, and the fragment was repositioned, followed by staged light curing.

A circumferential chamfer was then prepared at the fracture line, restored with flowable composite, and the surfaces were finished and polished.

Group II - Internal Dentinal Groove

In Group 2, an internal dentinal groove technique was used, where a 1 mm wide and 1 mm deep groove was prepared within both the fragment and remaining tooth structure. Adhesive was applied, followed by placement of nano-hybrid composite within the groove, and the fragment was reattached. The restoration was then finished and polished. This group was further divided into two subgroups.

Fig 3. Internal Dentinal Groove Preparation

Fig 4. Specimen after finishing and polishing

In Subgroup 2A, reattachment was performed using a 5th generation bonding agent with prior acid etching, followed by composite placement, fragment repositioning, staged light curing, and finishing.

In Subgroup 2B, a 7th generation bonding agent was used, followed by composite application, fragment reattachment, staged light curing, and final finishing and polishing.

3. Fracture of Restored Teeth

All four subgroups and the control group were tested for fracture resistance using a universal testing machine. The specimens were mounted in a jig, and force was applied in a labio-palatal direction at a 90° angle to the bonding line using 0.5 mm thick pointed (round end) stainless steel rod at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min.

The load at which each sample fractured was recorded and subjected to statistical analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Fracture strength was expressed as mean ± standard deviation, and normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test, confirming normal distribution. Therefore, parametric tests were applied, including one way ANOVA with post hoc Tukey test for intergroup and subgroup comparisons, and Student's t-test for intragroup comparisons, with the level of significance set at p < 0.05.

Result

The data followed a normal distribution, allowing the use of parametric tests. One way ANOVA showed a highly significant difference in fracture strength among the groups, with the control group exhibiting the highest values and no significant difference between external chamfer and internal dentinal groove techniques.

The comparison of mean fracture strength among the three main groups was performed using one-way ANOVA. Group 1 (n = 30) demonstrated a mean fracture strength of 372.11 ± 42.77, Group 2 (n = 30) showed a mean value of 383.47 ± 92.40, and

Group 3 (n = 15) exhibited the highest mean fracture strength of 655.17 ± 19.41. The intergroup comparison revealed a highly statistically significant difference among the groups (F = 108.87, p = 0.001), indicating that at least one group differed significantly from the others in terms of fracture strength. (Table 1)

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	P Value
Group 1	30	372.11	42.77	108.87	0.001*
Group 2	30	383.47	92.40		
Group 3	15	655.17	19.41		

Table 1: Comparison of Fracture strength in different groups

The mean fracture strength among all five subgroups was compared using one-way ANOVA. Subgroup 1A showed a mean value of 412.05 ± 8.81, Subgroup 1B had 332.17 ± 17.12, Subgroup 2A had 293.06 ± 4.86, Subgroup 2B demonstrated 473.88 ± 12.17, and Subgroup 3 exhibited the highest mean fracture strength of 655.17 ± 19.41. The overall comparison revealed a highly statistically significant difference among the subgroups (F = 1656.36, p = 0.001). Among all subgroups, Subgroup 3 demonstrated the highest fracture strength, whereas Subgroup 2A exhibited the lowest. (Table 2)

Subgroup	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	P value
Subgroup 1A	15	412.05	8.81	1656.36	0.001*
Subgroup 1B	15	332.17	17.12		
Subgroup 2A	15	293.06	4.86		
Subgroup 2B	15	473.88	12.17		
Subgroup 3	15	655.17	19.41		

Table 2: Comparison of Fracture strength in different sub-group

The fracture strength varied among the tested subgroups. Subgroup 3 showed the highest fracture strength (100%), followed by Subgroup 2B (72.3%) and Subgroup 1A (62.9%). Lower values were observed in Subgroup 1B (50.7%) and Subgroup 2A (44.7%), with Subgroup 2A demonstrating the lowest fracture resistance. Overall, the results indicate that Subgroup 3 exhibited the greatest fracture strength, while Subgroup 2A showed the weakest performance. The fracture strength increases notably from Subgroup 2A → 1B → 1A → 2B → 3.

Graph 1: Strength recovery of restored teeth (%)

Discussion

The restoration of fractured anterior teeth using fragment reattachment represents a highly conservative and effective approach that preserves natural tooth structure while restoring aesthetics, function, and mechanical integrity.³ Fracture strength is a key determinant of the long-term success of such restorations, as it reflects the ability of the reattached fragment to withstand functional and traumatic forces. In the present in vitro study, the influence of two reattachment techniques external chamfer and internal dentinal groove and two bonding systems 5th and 7th generation adhesives was evaluated.

Advances in adhesive dentistry, including acid-etch techniques and modern bonding agents, have significantly improved bonding effectiveness and clinical outcomes. However, no reattachment technique can completely restore the strength of an intact tooth due to the presence of an adhesive interface, which may act as a zone of weakness.^{4,5}

The findings of this study demonstrated that both the reattachment technique and the bonding system significantly influence fracture resistance. Although no statistically significant difference was observed between the two main techniques, subgroup analysis revealed important variations.

The external chamfer technique showed superior performance when used with the 5th generation bonding agent, likely due to enhanced enamel etching and micromechanical retention provided by the total etch system.⁶ In contrast, the internal dentinal groove technique performed better with the 7th generation bonding agent, possibly due to improved adaptation and infiltration of the self-etch adhesive within the prepared groove, reducing technique sensitivity and enhancing stress distribution.⁷

Among all experimental groups, the combination of internal dentinal groove and 7th generation bonding agent demonstrated the highest fracture strength, indicating a synergistic effect between internal reinforcement and simplified adhesive application.⁸

These results were consistent with previous studies that highlight the importance of both mechanical design and adhesive strategy

in improving fracture resistance. Techniques such as internal grooves increase bonding surface area and provide mechanical interlocking, while modern adhesives enhance hybrid layer formation and bond durability.⁹

Despite certain limitations inherent to in vitro studies, such as the use of artificially sectioned teeth, the methodology provided a standardized and reliable comparison.

Overall, the study emphasized that careful selection of reattachment technique and bonding system is crucial for optimizing the strength, durability, and clinical success of fragment reattachment procedures.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this in vitro study, fragment reattachment is a conservative and effective option for anterior tooth fractures, although no technique fully restores the strength of intact teeth. All methods showed acceptable fracture resistance, with outcomes influenced by both the reattachment technique and bonding agent. Fifth generation bonding agents performed better with the external chamfer technique, while seventh generation bonding agents showed superior results with the internal dentinal groove, which exhibited the highest fracture strength overall. Hence, appropriate selection of technique and bonding system is essential, and further long-term clinical studies are needed.

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